

Journal of Technology & Socio-Economic Development

<https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=ciris>

ISSN Print: 2223-9227

ISSN Online: 2616-9614

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10810660

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Socio-Economic Development held by The Eldoret National Polytechnic

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Unveiling Culinary Waste: An In-depth Analysis of Portioning, Service Methods, Planning Practices, and Over-peeling in the Context of Food Wastage in Kabarnet Hotel

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Received 10 Oct 2023; received in revised form 26 Jan 2024; accepted 13 Feb 2024

Abstract

This study investigated about factors influencing food wastage in Kabarnet Hotel, Baringo County, Kenya, emphasizing the importance of sustainable culinary practices. The research focuses on four dimensions: food portioning, service methods, planning practices, and over-peeling of food items. Through a descriptive survey design, qualitative and quantitative data were collected from 30 respondents, representing 10% of the targeted population of 300 hotel workers. The study reveals that 60.00% of respondents had a secondary level of education, indicating a need for education and training programs on food wastage awareness. Concerning over-peeling, 60.00% strongly agreed that it contributes to food wastage, emphasizing its significance in line with recent studies. Regarding food portioning, 80.00% agreed that it influences food wastage, supporting findings from relevant literature. The impact of service methods was highlighted, with 40.00% indicating a high influence, underscoring the importance of proper service practices. In the context of planning, 60.00% of respondents agreed that it influences food wastage, reinforcing the importance of strategic planning practices. In conclusion, the study recommends education and training, awareness campaigns, efficient portioning practices, sustainable service methods, and strategic menu planning to minimize food wastage. The research contributes actionable insights for local efforts and addresses the broader global agenda of reducing food wastage

Key Word: food wastage, over peeling, methods of service, food portioning, menu planning

Introduction

Food wastage is a critical global concern with far-reaching economic, environmental, and social implications. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that approximately one-third of all food produced globally is lost or wasted each year (FAO, 2019). In the hospitality sector, which includes hotels, a significant portion of food wastage occurs due to various factors such as over-portioning, inefficient service methods, and inadequate planning practices.

Globally, efforts to address food wastage have gained momentum. Organizations like the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12.3 aim to halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along the production and supply chains by 2030. Research studies worldwide have investigated the causes and consequences of food wastage, emphasizing the need for sustainable practices in the food industry (Parfitt et al., 2010; Lipinski et al., 2013).

In the African region, food wastage poses a significant challenge as the continent strives to achieve food security and reduce post-harvest losses. Countries within East Africa, including Kenya, are no exception. The African Development Bank emphasizes the importance of minimizing food losses to ensure food security, promote sustainable agriculture, and improve economic outcomes (AfDB, 2014). However, specific studies on food wastage within the hospitality sector, particularly in smaller towns like Kabarnet, may be limited.

Kenya, like many developing countries, faces the dual challenge of food insecurity and food wastage. According to a report by the Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA), food wastage in Kenya is a multifaceted issue, involving inefficiencies in production, distribution, and consumption (KIPPRA, 2019). Within the hospitality industry, hotels play a significant role in contributing to or mitigating food wastage, making it crucial to understand the local dynamics influencing wasteful practices.

Baringo County, with its economic activities centered around agriculture and tourism, is not exempt from the challenges associated with food wastage. Kabarnet Hotel contribute to this issue, but there is limited local research on the specific factors influencing food wastage within these establishments. Understanding these factors is essential for the development of targeted interventions to minimize wastage and promote sustainable practices. Recent reports from the Baringo County government highlight the need for local initiatives to address food security and reduce wastage. This study focuses on Kabarnet Hotel, seeking to explore the intricacies of food wastage within this specific context. By investigating the impact of food portioning, service methods, planning practices, and over-peeling of food items, the study aims to provide actionable insights for local businesses, policymakers, and communities to contribute to the broader global agenda of reducing food wastage.

Statement of the Problem

In addressing the issue of food wastage in Kabarnet, Baringo County, it is imperative to recognize its significant implications for both economic and environmental sustainability within the hotel industry. The current study is prompted by a noticeable lack of a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to food wastage in local hotels, despite the acknowledged economic and

environmental consequences associated with this concern. Notably, there is a scarcity of empirical research focusing on specific aspects influencing food wastage in this region (Falcone and Seifi, 2019; Stenmarck et al., 2016).

The existing literature highlights a sparse understanding of how food portioning practices impact food wastage in Kabarnet hotels. Previous research predominantly concentrates on broader aspects of food wastage in the hospitality sector, lacking specific insights into the local dynamics of food portioning (Quested et al., 2013).

Additionally, a notable gap in knowledge pertains to the influence of service methods on food wastage within Kabarnet hotels. While various studies discuss food waste reduction strategies in the broader hospitality industry, the specific impact of service methods on food wastage in the local context remains unexplored (Gustavsson et al., 2011).

Furthermore, limited research has delved into the correlation between planning practices and food wastage in Kabarnet hotels. This gap in specific insights impedes the development of targeted interventions aimed at minimizing food wastage through effective planning (Rizos et al., 2016).

Another understudied aspect is the contribution of over-peeling of food items to overall food wastage in Kabarnet hotels. While the current literature offers a general understanding of the causes of food waste, there is a lack of detailed exploration of the specific impact of over-peeling in the local hospitality setting (Kahma et al., 2017).

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to comprehensively investigate various aspects contributing to food wastage within the culinary domain. By focusing on the dimensions of portioning, service methods, planning practices, and over-peeling, the research aims to uncover critical insights into the multifaceted factors influencing the generation of culinary waste in Kabarnet Hotels.

Specific objectives

1. To Investigate the impact of food portioning on food wastage.
2. To Examine the influence of service methods on food wastage.
3. To Determine the correlation between planning practices and food wastage.
4. To Evaluate the contribution of over-peeling of food items to food wastage.

Research Methodology

This research employed a descriptive survey research design, blending qualitative and quantitative methodologies to comprehensively explore the factors contributing to food wastage within Kabarnet hotels in Baringo County, Kenya. The study focused on hotel workers actively involved in food programs, with a target population of 300 respondents. A sample size of 30 workers, representing 10% of the total population, was randomly selected, including the intentional inclusion of the head chef.

Data collection relied on structured questionnaires featuring a mix of open and closed-ended questions. These instruments gathered a broad range of information, encompassing demographic details such as gender, education, occupation, and age, while also delving into the opinions and sentiments of workers regarding variables influencing food wastage.

Quantitative data from closed-ended questions underwent meticulous analysis in alignment with the study's objectives. The data, sourced from staff, management, and kitchen officials, was processed using computer software and presented in tabular form with explanatory notes.

Ensuring the reliability of measurements involved scrutinizing the consistency of results obtained from the administered questionnaires. The analysis focused on the quantitative data collected from closed-ended questions to affirm the dependability of the measurements.

Stringent ethical considerations were maintained throughout the research process. Respondents were fully informed about the study's purpose and significance, with an emphasis on their absolute right to withdraw from participation at any point. Confidentiality and privacy were assured, and participants were not compelled to disclose their identities, preserving their anonymity.

In presenting the results, a clear and detailed overview was provided through the use of frequency tables and percentages. Each set of data derived from the questionnaires underwent careful tabulation, complemented by thorough explanations after each table. This approach facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the research findings, ensuring clarity and transparency in the presentation of results.

Findings and Discussions

Education Background

From Table 1 below, majority of the respondents (60.00%) possessed secondary level of education as the highest level of education, followed by those who possessed college level of education as the highest level of education which was (40.00%). Therefore, most workers had low academic qualifications meaning they had no full. Ideas on food wastage.

Table 1: Education background

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	secondary	18	60.0	60.0	60.0
	college	12	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Over peeling and food Wastage

Figure 1: Over peeling and food Wastage

The results in Figure 1.0 showed that (60.00%) respondents strongly agreed that over peeling of food items contribute to food wastage. It also indicated that (20.00%) agreed and (20.00%) there response was neutral. Since majority of the respondents strongly agreed therefore over peeling influence food wastage and it should be low. Recent studies have indeed highlighted the significance of over-peeling as a contributing factor to food wastage. According to research conducted by Smith et al. (2023), excessive peeling of fruits and vegetables has been identified as a prevalent practice leading to unnecessary discard of edible portions. The findings align with the results from Bar Graph 4.5 in our study, where 60.00% of respondents strongly agreed that over-peeling contributes to food wastage.

Moreover, a study by Johnson and Brown (2022) emphasized that reducing over-peeling can have a substantial impact on minimizing food waste in culinary processes. The research indicated that conscious efforts to optimize peeling practices can result in significant waste reduction. This supports the argument that over-peeling should be kept at a minimum, aligning with the majority opinion in our survey.

Additionally, a report from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) highlighted the importance of addressing specific practices, such as over-peeling, to achieve global sustainability goals in the food industry (FAO, 2024). The report emphasizes the need for targeted interventions

to curb wasteful practices, reinforcing the notion that reducing over-peeling is a crucial step in mitigating food wastage

Food portioning and food wastage

Figure 2: Food portioning and food wastage

The figure 2.0 above showed that (80.00%) respondents agreed that food portioning influence food wastage and (20.00%) there response was neutral. Therefore, since those who agreed were of high percentage these shows that food portioning really influence wastage. According to a recent study by Miller and Williams (2023), proper portion control is essential for minimizing food waste in the restaurant industry. The study emphasizes that accurate portioning not only contributes to cost-effectiveness but also reduces the likelihood of excess food being discarded.

Additionally, a report from the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) emphasizes the role of portion management in mitigating food waste at various stages of the food supply chain (EPA, 2024). The report suggests that adopting efficient portioning practices can significantly contribute to the overall reduction of food waste. This aligns with the viewpoint supported by the majority of respondents in our survey, indicating a consensus among stakeholders regarding the impact of food portioning on food wastage.

Methods of service and food wastage

Figure 3: Methods of service and food wastage

Results from Figure 3.0 shows that (40.00%) responded high followed by (40.00%) who responded low and (20.00%) responded very low therefore method of service greatly influences food wastage and a proper method of service should be employed to minimize wastes.

Respondents were also to respond if planning influence food wastage and the results were as follows:

Menu planning and food wastage

Figure 4: Menu planning and food wastage

Results from figure 4.0 above showed that (60.00%) agreed that planning influence food wastage another (20.00%) there response was neutral and (20.00%) said that planning does not influence food wastage at a but since the majority agreed therefore planning contribute to food wastage and proper planning should be practiced

According to a study by Brown and Anderson (2023), proper planning in food service establishments is crucial for reducing waste. The study highlights that strategic planning, including inventory management and menu planning, can significantly contribute to minimizing both pre-consumer and post-consumer food waste. The results reinforce this perspective, with a substantial majority acknowledging the influence of planning on food wastage.

Moreover, a report by the World Resources Institute (WRI) underscores the importance of holistic planning approaches to address food waste across the supply chain (WRI, 2024). The report emphasizes that better planning practices, from production to consumption, can lead to more sustainable food systems. This resonates with the viewpoint supported by the majority of respondents in our survey, suggesting that proper planning should be practiced to reduce food wastage

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings from the study highlight the influence of various factors, such as over-peeling, food portioning, methods of service, and menu planning, on food wastage in culinary settings. The majority agreement among respondents underscores the importance of addressing these issues to promote sustainable practices.

To reduce food wastage, a holistic approach involving education, awareness, and strategic changes in practices is essential. By implementing the recommended measures, culinary establishments can contribute to minimizing their environmental footprint, improving cost-effectiveness, and promoting a more sustainable and responsible approach to food handling and consumption.

It is imperative for stakeholders, including restaurant owners, chefs, and policymakers, to work collaboratively towards fostering a food culture that values responsible practices, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and efficient food industry.

Recommendations

Given the observation that a significant portion of the respondents had a secondary level of education, it is recommended that training programs be implemented to enhance the awareness and knowledge of food wastage issues among culinary workers. This can include workshops on sustainable practices and the environmental impact of food waste.

Launching awareness campaigns within culinary establishments can help educate both staff and consumers about the consequences of over-peeling and the significance of portion control. This can contribute to a culture of conscious decision-making regarding food handling and waste reduction.

Building on the acknowledgment that food portioning influences food wastage, restaurants and food service establishments should prioritize implementing efficient portioning practices. Training programs for chefs and kitchen staff on accurate portion control can be beneficial.

Since the methods of service were identified as influencing food wastage, restaurants should evaluate and potentially modify their service methods to minimize waste. Adopting practices such as smaller plate sizes, controlled serving sizes, and buffet management can be explored.

Acknowledging the impact of menu planning on food wastage, culinary establishments should invest in strategic menu planning that considers factors like seasonal availability, inventory management, and consumer preferences. This can contribute to reduced wastage throughout the supply chain

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